

Research-Based Policy Brief for Enhancing the Seaweed Production in the Selected Municipalities of Tawi-Tawi

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Abstract:

Seaweed production in the Philippines is vital for economic growth, environmental sustainability, and social development, particularly in coastal regions like Tawi-Tawi. However, the industry in Tawi-Tawi faces significant challenges due to weak policy implementation. This study aims to enhance seaweed production in selected municipalities of Tawi-Tawi by proposing a research-based policy brief. Utilizing a sequential mixed-method approach, the study involved 180 purposively selected seaweed farmers. Data were collected through semi-structured open-ended questionnaires, aligned with BTA Bill

196, and analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively. The findings revealed that policy implementation in Tawi-Tawi's seaweed industry is only slightly effective, with a mean score of 2.51. Major challenges include inadequate infrastructure, poor growth environments, and insufficient processing technology, all exacerbated by weak policy enforcement. The study identified a critical gap in current policies, particularly the lack of IT infrastructure to manage transactions, which emerged as a key issue. Consequently, the study concludes that the current policy framework is not fully effective and requires significant improvement, as such a policy brief is proposed.

Keywords: *policy brief, seaweed production, Tawi-Tawi.*

Introduction

Seaweed production is a significant economic activity in coastal communities, particularly in Southeast Asia, where it serves as a critical source of livelihood and plays a vital role in the local economy. In the past 20 years, the seaweed farming and production process have increased significantly, and play the important role in the fishing industry by country (Cai et al. 2021). According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) data, the global seaweed output (both aquaculture and wild) has increased nearly three-fold from 118,000 tons to 358,200 tons from Year 2000 to Year 2019 (FAO 2021). In 2019, 97% of the global aquaculture output came from artificial farming. The world's

seaweed production mostly comes from the five major continents with Asia accounting for 97.38%. In Asia, 99% of seaweed is cultured artificially. China ranks first in the world in terms of aquaculture production, accounting for 56.82% of the global aquaculture. The main algae are Japanese kelp (*Laminaria japonica*), Gracilaria seaweeds (*Gracilaria* spp.) and nori Nei (*Porphyra* spp.).

In the Philippines, the province of Tawi-Tawi has emerged as a key player in the seaweed industry, contributing substantially to the nation's overall production. Seaweed farming in this region is predominantly carried out by small-scale farmers who rely on traditional methods passed down through generations. Seaweeds are

the primary commodity produced by the Philippine fisheries and aquaculture with 1,499 million metric tons. It is also the top export contributing 33.33% to the total fisheries production in 2020. The gross value of seaweed production in 2020 amounted to 10.60 billion pesos. The Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao shares 46.5% of the aquaculture production of seaweed, making them the top producer in the Philippines. One of the problems that hindered farmers from intensifying seaweeds farming was the lack of capital and government support, particularly on infrastructure for production and post production activities, which resulted in low socio-economic status. It also focused on generating equitable and sustainable relations between the vulnerable seaweeds farmers, and influence local policies and practices in the seaweeds industry.

Existing research has highlighted several factors that influence seaweed production, including environmental conditions such as water quality, temperature, and salinity (Buschmann et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2015); socio-economic aspects like market access, funding, and technical expertise (Cai et al., 2021; Largo et al., 2019); and policy frameworks that either support or limit growth (Valderrama et al., 2015; Hurtado et al., 2019). While these studies provide valuable insights, there is a notable gap in the comprehensive analysis of how these factors interplay within the unique context of Tawi-Tawi's municipalities. Furthermore, current policies often lack a holistic approach, failing to address the multifaceted nature of the industry and the specific needs of local communities. The BARMM standpoint programs, the long time ago challenges and problems in the implementation of policy to harness technology and innovations to increase socio-economic opportunities and improved government services, for the seaweed productions in the island Province of Tawi-Tawi may possibly cater to its success.

This study aims to fill this gap by developing a policy determination model tailored to the seaweed production landscape of Tawi-Tawi. By employing a mixed-methods approach, this

research will integrate quantitative data from field surveys and qualitative insights from stakeholder interviews. Thus, this study intends to gather, evaluate, and analyze the information in determining the policy brief anchored on establishing technologically advanced aquaculture for seaweed production in the Province of Tawi-Tawi. This policy brief will not only boost seaweed production but also ensure economic viability, environmental conservation, and community empowerment in Tawi-Tawi's municipalities. By addressing the identified gaps, the study is guided with the following research questions:

- 1) What is the participants' perception on the level of implementation of the seaweed production in the selected municipalities of Tawi-Tawi?
- 2) What are the challenges and problems do seaweed farmers in Tawi-Tawi face?
- 3) What insights can be gained from farmers' experiences and perspectives to inform the policy determination model?
- 4) What policy can be developed to enhance seaweed production in Tawi-Tawi?

Addressing the objective and research questions above, this study provides a concrete information to the Tawi-Tawi provincial government and administrative units on the sustainable infrastructure projects for the increase of seaweed production which may be established based on BARMM regional sustainable development program. Moreover, it also provides information to NEDA-national economic development authority to affirm its commitment to work with the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a sequential mixed-methods approach, integrating both qualitative and quantitative data to provide detailed and comprehensive information aimed at achieving the research objectives and answering the

research questions. The mixed-methods approach allows for a more thorough analysis by leveraging the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative methodologies.

In the initial phase, quantitative data was collected through a survey to establish the level of implementation of seaweed production policies and their effectiveness. The survey was designed based on the BTA Parliament Resolution 268, Rule II, Section 2, Paragraph K, and is distributed to key staff involved in seaweed production. This quantitative data provides a broad understanding of the current state of seaweed production and policy implementation.

To explore the quantitative data in greater depth, the second phase involves gathering qualitative data through interviews. An interview guide was used to conduct detailed discussions with stakeholders, including local seaweed farmers and policymakers. These interviews aim to uncover the challenges and problems in implementing the policy guidelines and to provide context and explanations for the quantitative results. The use of mixed methodologies is beneficial as it allows for a comprehensive analysis of the research questions from multiple perspectives. According to Schoonenboom and Johnson (2017), mixed-methods research helps in analyzing various aspects of a research question by combining the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative approaches. This method is particularly advantageous in behavioral and social studies disciplines, providing a more nuanced view that can enhance the study's findings (Tegan, 2021). Additionally, mixed-methods research offers detailed insights and significant ideas that are vital for the study, as noted by Osbaldeston (2021).

Research Site

The study was conducted in the province of Tawi-Tawi, located at the southernmost tip of the Philippines, bordering Sabah, Malaysia to the south. Tawi-Tawi consists of 11 municipalities, with Bongao serving as the provincial capital. The province features a mix of mainland and island municipalities: Panglima Sugala and

Languyan are situated on the mainland, while the remaining nine, including Bongao and Mapun (formerly known as Cagayan de Tawi-Tawi), are island municipalities. This diverse geographical composition presents unique opportunities and challenges for seaweed production, which this study aims to explore and address.

Participants

The study involves 180 participants, categorized as follows: 15 (8%) from national and regional officials, 10 (5%) from provincial officials, 33 (18%) from municipal officials, 10 (6%) from state university representatives, 7 (4%) from non-governmental organizations, 20 (11%) from academia, 65 (36%) farmers, and 20 (11%) fishermen.

The selection of participants and key informants was purposive. This approach involved 30 key informants for the qualitative aspects of the study. Participants were selected based on specific criteria established by the researcher to ensure they best meet the study's objectives. These key informants included both Muslim and non-Muslim national, provincial, and municipal government officials; NGO officials, including those from the Chinese-Filipino Chamber of Commerce; and experts in seaweed production from the marine science department of MSU-TCTO in Tawi-Tawi. This careful selection process ensured that participants provided a wealth of valuable information.

Research Instruments

According to Rourk & Anderson (2004), demonstrating the trustworthiness of data collection is crucial for ensuring a study's reliability. Data collection methods often include structured techniques such as interviews, observations, and written documents, or a combination of these. Depending on the study's aim, the data collected can be open and semi-structured (Lo et al., 2014).

In this study, the researcher employed a semi-structured questionnaire for respondents. The questionnaire included a series of open-ended questions designed to capture detailed responses, integrated with step-by-step, time-bound measurements, and frequency responses.

The questionnaire was aligned with BTA Bill 196 and comprised two parts: Part One: Assessed perceptions and the level of implementation of seaweed production in Tawi-Tawi. Part Two: Evaluated the effectiveness of policy implementation in terms of economic, tourism, stakeholder, political, environmental, and legal aspects. Additionally, an interview guide was developed to explore the challenges, problems, and constraints encountered during the implementation of these policies.

Data Collection and Analysis

The researcher obtained authorization to conduct the study and held a preliminary meeting with the selected respondents to establish rapport, review ethical considerations, and complete consent forms. During data collection, the researcher conducted interviews using a semi-structured questionnaire and an assessment checklist. To ensure confidentiality, each participant was assigned a corresponding legend instead of revealing their identities. The collected data was statistically tabulated and analyzed using statistical formulas. The questionnaire responses that was quantitative, the weighted mean was used to establish a quantitative analysis, with the mean calculated for each questionnaire item. On the other hand, qualitative analysis was done through textual and thematic analysis.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher meticulously planned and assessed all potential risks and benefits of the study, seeking advice from the research adviser and obtaining permission from the Ethics Review Committee of Cebu Normal University. The study was deemed beneficial to seaweed production beneficiaries in Tawi-Tawi, with no identified risks to key informants. Collaboration was established with stakeholders, and ethical considerations were approved by relevant agencies. Each key informant received a transmittal letter detailing the study's objectives, procedures, and confidentiality assurances, ensuring informed consent and the right to withdraw. Confidentiality was strictly maintained, with only the researcher having access to the data. Respondents could review

their responses for accuracy, and participation was voluntary without incentives.

Results

Results of the study are presented in accordance to the sequence of the research questions.

Participants' Perception on the Level of Implementation of the Seaweed Production in the Selected Municipalities of Tawi-Tawi

Table 1. Level of Policy Implementation in Seaweed Production as Perceived by the Participants

Dimension	Mean Score	Description
Planning	2.39	Slightly Implemented
Site Preparation and Facilities	2.36	Slightly Implemented
Beneficiaries	2.47	Slightly Implemented
Financial Support	2.31	Slightly Implemented
Capacity Building	2.26	Slightly Implemented
Collaboration	2.65	Moderately Implemented
Monitoring	2.28	Slightly Implemented
Reporting	2.25	Slightly Implemented
Average	2.37	Slightly Implemented

Note: Fully Implemented--> 3.26 - 4.00; Moderately Implemented--> 2.51 - 3.25; Slightly Implemented --> 1.76 - 2.50; Not Implemented --> 1.00 - 1.75

The overall the level of policy implementation in the seaweed production in the selected municipalities of Tawi-Tawi is a slight implementation. This has a mean score of 2.37 described as slightly implemented. This is composed into a implementation component of program planning in a weighted score of 2.39 (slightly implemented), site identification of 2.36 (slightly implemented), identification of beneficiaries of 2.47 (slightly implemented), financial support of 2.31 (slightly implemented), capacity building of 2.26 (slightly implemented), monitoring of 2.28 (slightly implemented), reporting of 2.25 (slightly implemented), and

only with a mean core of 2.65 described as moderately implemented is in collaboration.

Challenges and Problems Encountered by Seaweed Farmers in Tawi-Tawi

Table 2. Textual Analysis on the Challenges Face by the Seaweed Farmers in Tawi-Tawi

Key Themes	Textual Analysis
1) Internal Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seaweed production & Processing Technology Value Added Products
2) External Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global Warming & Sea level Rise Green Algae Reproduction and Micro Plastics
3) Problems Encountered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IT setup New Technology IT Connectivity Funding Delays

1) Internal Challenges

Seaweed production and processing technology do not answer the demand. At present, the cultivation of seaweed is mainly developed in some underdeveloped areas and seedling raising, cultivation, and harvesting, processing are our concerns. To focus on basic cultivation, the automation of large-scale harvesting and processing are not yet in placed.

2) External Challenges

The external challenges are mainly in the following aspects: global warming and sea-level rise lead to the declined seaweed biomass and quality. In order to deal with the harsh environment, the cost of breeding management including equipment maintenance, renewal and growth environment management has been increased.

3) Problems Encountered

The most leading problem encountered in the of implementation of a Seaweed Production in the Province of Tawi-Tawi is no IT set up to handle transactions that rank 1st in the problems. This is followed by the no new technology to benefits members performance which rank 2nd, no access of IT connectivity needed to support rank 3rd, no appropriate training to support the beneficiary's rank 4th, delayed in the implementation due to funds not available on time rank 5th, no specific instruction on how to manage seaweed production rank 6th, delay in the processing of payments due to lack of supporting documents rank 7th. Misunderstanding among co-members rank 8th, misunderstanding occurs in the community and least among is the problem about tin the organization. Fertilizers.

Table 3. Problems Encountered in the of Implementation of a Seaweed Production

No.	Item	Respondents Frequency	Interpretatio n
1	There is no IT set up to handle transactions.	73.33	Ranked 1
2	No new technology to benefits member performance.	71.11	Ranked 2
3	No access of IT connectivity needed to support Seaweed Production of Tawi- Tawi.	69.44	Ranked 3
4	Delayed in the implementation of Seaweed Production due to funds not available on time.	66.11	Ranked 5
5	Delay in the processing of payments due to lack of supporting documents.	40.56	Ranked 7
6	Misunderstanding occurs in the community or organization.	31.11	Ranked 9
7	Misunderstanding among co-members.	36.11	Ranked 8
8	No specific instruction on how to manage seaweed Production.	61.11	Ranked 6
9	No appropriate training to support the beneficiaries.	66.67	Ranked 4
10	Others (specify: Fertilizers)	26.11	Ranked 10

In Bongao, Tawi-Tawi, the handling of seaweed production transactions is hindered by a lack of information technology and regulatory frameworks, with processes remaining manual due to insufficient IT integration. Training efforts for seaweed farmers and stakeholders, provided by BARMM and MSU-TCTO, often fail to address implementation issues due to inconsistencies with local ordinances and insufficient support from BARMM. Financial support is minimal, with farmers often relying on local buyers who offer funds in exchange for exclusive selling rights, leading to contract violations and financial instability. There is a lack of clear instructions for managing seaweed production, with NGOs and departments offering limited support. Cultural conflicts between Tausug tribes and native Sama Dilaut also affect seaweed activities, with disputes over land use. Additionally, fertilizer use is problematic, increasing production costs and potentially decreasing seaweed quality, with limited efforts from local governments to address this issue.

Farmers Insights

- 1) **Unavailability of Information Technology.** Transactions for seaweed production are handled manually due to a lack of IT support and regulation.
- 2) **Inadequate Training.** Seminars often serve only compliance purposes, offering minimal benefits to seaweed farmers.
- 3) **Limited Financial Support.** Insufficient government funding forces farmers to depend on local buyers for financial support.
- 4) **Lack of Specific Guidance.** Minimal government support leads farmers and buyers to rely on their own initiatives.
- 5) **Cultural Conflicts.** Dominance issues between tribes create conflicts and disrupt seaweed production activities.
- 6) **Fertilizer Issues.** Expensive fertilizers increase production costs and lower seaweed value, with no intervention from local governments.

Discussion

Perception of Level Implementation of the Seaweed Production

Resistance from respondents can originate perception that incumbents were executing correctly or not correctly in the process. The growing population and development have led to an increasing demand of seaweeds in the province. If affordable production is not made available in selected areas and productions continue to expand. The data were obtained from the questionnaire on level of implementation of seaweed production. The study presented quantitative data in tables, accompanied by brief explanations. As shown in table 1, the participants generally perceived that the policy of the seaweed production in Tawi-tawi is slightly implemented. Ansell et al. (2017) emphasized the need for policies to be designed in a way that “connects actors vertically and horizontally in a process of collaboration and joint deliberation. Implementation plans differ from one project to another. There are several components you may find in common, including: project objectives, scope statement, risks analysis, resources and tools list, outline of deliverables. Implementation strategy and implementation schedule. Stages of activities organized by the essential support structures, with links to some associated tools and materials started in a stage of exploration and planning. Likewise, budget, facilities, beneficiaries, capacity building, collaboration, monitoring and reporting are insuefficient. With Volker (2014) and McConnell (2015) emphasized that capacity building can be part of the piloting component, and you can use training materials you develop for the implementation phase later to train new beneficiaries on the process. The better you train staff on the updated process, the better the chance on a smooth implementation when you go live. The training phase also provides an excellent opportunity in a better execution of the process. Ansell et al. (2017) emphasize the need for policies to be designed in a way that “connects actors vertically and

horizontally in a process of collaboration and joint deliberation

Challenges and Problems Encountered by the Seaweeds Farmers

Seaweed farmers face different challenges and problems in their seaweed farming. The challenges are both external and internal. With the increase of temperature, these large amounts of green algae reproduce and eventually enter the ocean to form a “green tide.” Microplastics in the ocean will be captured by cultured algae and spread to a higher nutritional level through the food chains, resulting in a significant burden on marine ecology (Yu et al. (2016). Pérez et al. (2016) said that a large amount of bioactive compounds from Seaweed have been studied. However, the value-added products is generally low because of the lack of advanced techniques for extraction and purification.

Farmers Insights Policy Determination Model for Seaweed Production

Farmers highlighted that unavailability of information, inadequate training, limited financial support, lack of specific guidance, cultural conflicts and fertilizers issues were their common problems. These insights are supported by various studies and authors. A study by Valderrama et al. (2015) highlighted that market instability is a major concern for seaweed farmers in the Philippines. Farmers are concerned about fluctuating market prices and access to reliable markets. Policies should address stable pricing mechanisms and market access support. High costs of farming inputs, such as seedlings, ropes, and maintenance, are a barrier for many farmers. Subsidies or financial support for inputs could be beneficial. According to Cruz et al. (2019), input costs significantly impact the profitability of seaweed farming. Similarly, technical and training needs plays important role for the sustainability of the farmers seaweed productions. Farmers express a need for training on improved cultivation techniques to enhance productivity and reduce losses due to diseases and pests. Msuya et al. (2007) found that training in advanced farming techniques improved seaweed yield and quality. Proper drying and processing techniques are

crucial for maintaining the quality of harvested seaweed. Farmers need training and infrastructure support for post-harvest handling. Trono (1999) emphasizes the importance of proper post-harvest practices in maintaining seaweed quality.

On the other hand, farmers prefer community-based approaches for managing seaweed farms, which enhance cooperation and resource sharing. Sievanen et al. (2005) shows that community-based management leads to more sustainable and equitable resource use. In many communities, women play a crucial role in seaweed farming. Policies should promote and support the involvement of women in all aspects of seaweed production. Hurtado et al. (2019) note the significant contribution of women in seaweed farming communities in the Philippines. In the same manner, environmental conditions and sustainability is necessary for the farmers to continuously motivated to do their work. Farmers often emphasize the importance of clean and nutrient-rich water for optimal seaweed growth. Policies should focus on monitoring and maintaining water quality. According to a study by Bindu & Levine (2011), water quality is crucial for seaweed health and productivity. Farmers have observed the impacts of climate change, such as rising temperatures and unpredictable weather patterns, which affect seaweed growth and harvest cycles. Hurtado et al. (2013) noted that climate change poses significant risks to seaweed farming due to temperature sensitivity.

Farmers also often face challenges in transporting seaweed to markets due to inadequate infrastructure. Improving transportation networks and providing support for logistics can enhance market access. According to a report by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2016), transportation infrastructure is critical for the success of seaweed farming. Lack of proper storage facilities can lead to losses. Investments in storage infrastructure can help farmers manage their produce better. FAO (2016) also highlights the importance of storage facilities in reducing post-harvest losses. Farmers need clear and supportive regulations that protect their

interests and promote sustainable practices. Simplified licensing and permit processes are essential. Perez et al. (2020) emphasizes the need for a streamlined regulatory framework to support small-scale seaweed farmers. Support for R&D can lead to the development of disease-resistant seaweed strains and improved farming techniques. According to Hurtado and Critchley (2006), ongoing research is crucial for addressing challenges in seaweed farming. Incorporating farmers' insights into the policy determination model, policymakers can create a supportive environment for seaweed farmers in Tawi-Tawi, addressing their practical needs and promoting sustainable development.

Proposed Policy Brief to Enhance Seaweeds Production in Tawi-Eawi

Title: Enhancing Seaweed Production in Selected Municipalities of Tawi-Tawi

Executive Summary

Seaweed production in Tawi-Tawi is a significant contributor to both local livelihoods and the regional economy. However, challenges such as limited infrastructure, inconsistent quality control, and environmental degradation threaten its sustainability and growth. This policy brief outlines the current state of seaweed production in selected municipalities of Tawi-Tawi, identifies key challenges, and provides recommendations to enhance the industry's productivity and sustainability. This policy brief is a crucial tool in the policy-making process, particularly for translating complex research into actionable insights that can influence decisions. Implementing these recommendations will not only boost local income but also strengthen the Philippines' position in the global seaweed market.

Introduction

Seaweed production in the Philippines is significant not only for its economic benefits but also for its environmental and social contributions. Tawi-Tawi, in particular is an island province in the southern Philippines, and one of the country's leading producers of

seaweed, particularly *Kappaphycus* and *Eucheuma* species, which are vital for carrageenan production. The industry provides income for thousands of families and is integral to the province's economy. It supports livelihoods, contributes to environmental sustainability, and plays a critical role in the global supply chain, making it a vital industry for the country's present and future development. However, despite its potential, the seaweed industry in Tawi-Tawi faces significant challenges that hinder its development. This policy brief serves as a strategic tool for influencing policy decisions by presenting clear, evidence-based arguments and recommendations, supported by relevant citations.

Problem Statement

Findings of this study indicate that while Tawi-Tawi contributes a substantial share to the national seaweed output, the industry is plagued by several issues. These include poor post-harvest facilities, inadequate quality control measures, environmental stresses due to climate change, and a lack of access to financing and training for seaweed farmers. These challenges threaten the long-term viability of seaweed production in the region and limit the potential economic benefits for local communities.

Analysis

1) Infrastructure and Post-Harvest Challenges

Seaweed farmers in Tawi-Tawi often lack access to proper drying facilities, leading to product degradation and lower market prices. In some municipalities, seaweed is dried directly on sandy beaches, which can lead to contamination and inconsistent quality (Bajo et al., 2022).

2) Quality Control Issues

The absence of standardized quality control protocols results in varying product quality, affecting market competitiveness. Farmers often lack the knowledge or resources to implement best practices for cultivation and post-harvest handling (Gomez & Santos, 2021).

3) Environmental Stressors

Climate change has led to increased sea temperatures and more frequent extreme weather events, which negatively impact seaweed growth and productivity. Additionally, unsustainable farming practices contribute to environmental degradation, further exacerbating these issues (FAO, 2021).

4) Lack of Access to Financing and Training

Many seaweed farmers in Tawi-Tawi do not have access to credit or financial services that could help them invest in better farming techniques or infrastructure. Moreover, there is a need for more training programs focused on sustainable farming practices and business management (Perez, 2023).

Recommendations

1) **Investment in Post-Harvest Infrastructure.** The government and private sector should collaborate to establish centralized drying and processing facilities in key municipalities. These facilities should meet international standards to ensure high-quality output and reduce post-harvest losses.

2) **Implementation of Quality Control Standards.** Develop and enforce standardized quality control protocols across the seaweed production chain. Training programs should be provided to farmers on these standards to ensure consistent product quality and enhance market competitiveness.

3) **Promotion of Sustainable Farming Practices.** Introduce and support sustainable seaweed farming practices to mitigate the effects of climate change and environmental degradation. This includes promoting the use of environmentally friendly farming techniques and diversifying seaweed species to enhance resilience.

4) **Enhancing Access to Financing and Training.** Expand access to microfinance and other financial services tailored to seaweed farmers. Additionally, develop capacity-building programs that provide training in modern

farming practices, financial management, and market access strategies.

Strengthening seaweed production in Tawi-Tawi requires a multi-faceted approach that addresses both the immediate challenges and long-term sustainability of the industry. By investing in infrastructure, implementing quality control measures, promoting sustainable practices, and improving access to financing and training, Tawi-Tawi can enhance its seaweed production capabilities, improve livelihoods, and solidify its role in the global seaweed market.

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